

African American Community Archives Theory

*"Research is formalized curiosity.
It is poking and prying with a purpose."* - Zora Neale Hurston

About Theory

African American Community Archives as Theory

The African American Community Archives Theory is based on a conceptual framework that aims to facilitate the archiving process within Black communities. It recognizes the importance of preserving and organizing information in a way that serves the specific needs and interests of these communities. By adopting this framework, librarians, archivists, and community historians can effectively document and protect the rich history, culture, and experiences of African Americans, ensuring that their stories are accurately represented through information work. Autoethnography serves as the guiding methodology, employing triangulation to incorporate diverse methods and tools in research and community settings.

The development and preservation of African American community archives are essential, as they serve as valuable primary resources for future generations to explore their roots and gain a profound understanding of their community's history. The foundational principles integrated theory for practical use within the African American community consist of information as work in community archives based on the following below.

- Develop a broad understanding of the cultural backgrounds and histories of African and African American peoples.
- Understanding the history of the African American community is essential for meaningful engagement.
- Foster community participation through collaborative initiatives.
- Employ survey methods to obtain valuable information from the local community.

Theoretical Objectives

- Analyze and expand upon the theoretical foundations of African American Community Archives.
- Apply the theoretical principles underlying African American Community Archives.
- Build information management practices of African American community archives.
- Develop and Build and Market a community archival project the community.

Through her doctoral dissertation research, kYmberly Keeton, who holds a Master of Library Science, a Certificate of Archivism, and a Ph.D., developed the African American Community Archives Theory. | African American Community Archives Theory © 2024 by kYmberly Keeton, M.L.S., C.A., Ph.D. is licensed under CC BY-NC-ND 4.0. To view a copy of this license, visit <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-nd/4.0/>

